

StarsEngines

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Keywords

Business, Collaborative Problem-solving, Project Management, Simulation-based Learning, Stakeholder Management, Strategic Decision-making, Systems Thinking

Figure 1. Example setup of StarsEngines during facilitated gameplay. The image is used for illustrative purposes only.

Introduction

StarsEngines is a digital simulation game developed in 2020 and significantly modified in 2024 under the leadership of Prof. Dr. Siegfried G. Zürn at Esslingen University of Applied Sciences. Designed to integrate systems thinking into project management education, the game provides an immersive, interactive learning environment for students and professionals. StarsEngines leverages the impactation® Method to emphasize the interdependencies within technical, organizational, and social systems (Zürn & Holzner, 2025).

Participants engage in realistic project scenarios that simulate the complexities of modern R&D project management in the automotive industry. Based on the findings of Bakhshi et al. (2016) and Morcov et al. (2020), project complexity scenarios have been created to challenge players to balance technical, strategic, and interpersonal skills while adapting to dynamic

conditions such as resource constraints and stakeholder shifts. The actions the players can take are selected based on the ICB4 competence areas (IPMA, 2015). StarsEngines has been applied successfully in academic training at various universities, demonstrating its versatility and effectiveness for project management training.

Facts

Release date:	2020; new version: 2024
Developer:	Prof. Dr. Siegfried G. Zürn and team, Esslingen University
Game type:	Digital Simulation
Number of players:	3–6 players per team
Format:	Classroom, online, and hybrid feasible
Time frame:	120–180 minutes
Languages:	English
Environment:	For digital play
Material:	Predefined scenarios, interactive dashboards, and instructional guides
Price:	Free for public education institutes, licensing agreements for others

Resonance & Criticism

No large-scale peer-reviewed empirical study of StarsEngines has yet been published; formal data collection is planned for 2025. Course-level evaluations across several universities report that StarsEngines is both engaging and highly transferable. In recent undergraduate cohorts at Esslingen, more than 90% of participants recommended its continued use, even though about 70% had never worked with a simulation before. They emphasize the game's lifelike pressure, the visibility of feedback loops, and the need for tight team coordination as major drivers of learning (Zürn & Brunner, 2021). Some players find the initial complexity daunting and request concise theory cues or quick-reference aids during play; others suggest either extending the run time or reducing the team size to allow deeper discussion. These enhancements have already been included in the current version.

Game Principle & Process

StarsEngines immerses players in a fictional yet realistic R&D project environment: a technology development initiative for a hybrid engine control unit. Participants assume the role of a project manager, tasked with achieving predefined objectives while navigating the complexities of the interdependent project system.

The game is structured into multiple rounds, each representing one month of project duration. Dynamic events, such as budget constraints and unforeseen technical setbacks, add layers of complexity, requiring adaptive decision-making. Players choose from a variety of actions, such as reallocating resources, addressing technical challenges, and engaging with stakeholders. These actions influence interconnected elements, including team dynamics, project

outcomes, and resource utilization. They also affect the occurrence and severity of new or recurring events (Zürn & Brunner, 2021).

By integrating the principles of the impactation® Method, StarsEngines emphasizes the systemic impact of decisions. Players must consider short- and long-term consequences to foster a holistic understanding of a project management dynamics. The game's iterative nature allows participants to refine strategies and improve outcomes over successive rounds.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

StarsEngines enables learners to think and act systemically in complex project environments. By steering a hybrid-engine R&D project through 12 monthly rounds, participants experience how every action – hiring staff, postponing a review, reallocating budget – impacts the whole system of cost, schedule, quality, and stakeholder satisfaction. They enhance their strategic foresight and decision-making skills under pressure through (1) diagnosing, reinforcing, and balancing feedback loops, (2) weighing short-term gains against long-term systemic impact, and (3) coordinating decisions in cross-functional teams where communication is as critical as analysis.

Facilitators play a central role in transforming these experiences into lasting insights. A 15-minute briefing introduces the impactation® framework, followed by a 5-minute video clip presenting the case and project framework. Micro-debriefings on a project dashboard after each round uncover potential deviations from project goals and prompt participants to consider next actions. In a 30–45-minute final discussion, the simulation results are reviewed, and observed patterns are linked to project management best practices.

As the game mechanics mirror real project pressures (resource scarcity, dynamic stakeholder behavior, and some accidental events) and the complexity can be adjusted by selecting different scenarios, StarsEngines is versatile across educational settings. It can be used in undergraduate and master-level project management courses, MBA and executive programmes, corporate talent training, and interdisciplinary team-building workshops. The digital format also supports full online delivery or hybrid realization.

Effectiveness

Feedback from participants highlights StarsEngines' effectiveness in bridging theoretical concepts with practical application. Students report increased awareness of systemic interdependencies, improved communication skills, and a deeper understanding of adaptive strategies. Structured debriefings at the end of the simulation further reinforce learning by encouraging reflection on decision-making processes and outcomes.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

StarsEngines relies heavily on facilitator guidance and structured debriefing to translate gameplay experiences into learning outcomes; without sufficient facilitation, key systems-thinking insights may remain implicit. In addition, the simulation's domain-specific focus on automotive R&D may limit immediate transferability to non-technical or non-industrial project contexts unless explicitly contextualized by instructors. However, similar simulations based on cases of different domains are available from the same author by request.

Reviewer(s): Barbara Holzner, Daniel Geist

Sources

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